

ORGANIZATION OF PROJECT WORK IN NATURAL SCIENCES USING THE 5E APPROACH

Rakhmonov U.U.

Methodologist on Physics and Astronomy, Navoiy Region Pedagogical Skills Center,
Independent Researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13926308>

Abstract. *This article describes the "5E Approach" (Engagement, Exploration, Explanation, Elaboration, Evaluation) model for the effective organization of project work on natural sciences. This approach is important in developing students' scientific research and developing their ability to learn independently. The article explains the content of each stage and their role in the project implementation process in detail. It also provides practical examples of using this pedagogical approach in teaching natural sciences. With the help of the 5E model, students actively acquire knowledge and develop creativity and critical thinking skills in solving scientific problems.*

Keywords: *project work, 5E model, engagement, research, explanation, application, evaluation, scientific phenomenon, debate, practical work, learning process, critical thinking, solving scientific problems.*

Introduction. It is known that a number of decisions have been made to develop natural sciences and improve education in new Uzbekistan. This study serves to implement the tasks defined in Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PR-4805 dated August 12, 2020 "On measures to improve the quality of continuous education and the effectiveness of science in the fields of chemistry and biology", in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan 484 dated June 11, 2019 "On approval of the Strategy for the conservation of biological diversity in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2019-2028" and in other regulatory and legal acts related to this activity. In 2023, schools specialized in mathematics, chemistry, biology and geology were created, teachers' qualifications were improved, and curricula were updated. As the President noted, without natural sciences, it will be difficult to develop modern technologies and achieve global achievements.

Moreover, much attention is also paid to international cooperation in the field of natural sciences and the creation of modern textbooks. The development of teachers' research skills and their training in new methods is defined as an important area in the public education system.

The 5E model is a modern approach used in the study of project work on natural sciences and includes five main stages (Table 1):

Step 1. Engagement - at this stage the teacher tries to attract the interest and attention of the students to the new topic. This process is carried out through questions and answers, examples and problems from real life. This helps the students to identify their knowledge and connect existing knowledge with new knowledge.

Step 2. Exploration. At this stage, students independently conduct experiments, collect information and investigate problems. Students discover new knowledge through scientific observations and practical experience, which further increases their interest.

Step 3. Explanation. At this stage, students analyze the data collected and explain new knowledge in their own words. The teacher helps them explain and guides them to express scientific concepts correctly.

Step 4. Elaboration - at this stage, students deepen the learned concepts and explore ways to apply them in other areas. At this stage, the application of new knowledge through projects and creative works plays an important role.

Step 5. Evaluation. At the last stage, students will have the opportunity to assess their knowledge and skills. At this stage, it is determined to what extent the knowledge has been mastered through tests, assessments and mutual analysis [1].

Table 1. Stages of organizing project work based on the 5E model

Stages of the 5E model.	Performing project work in traditional classes	Organization of project work classes based on the 5E model
Engagement	Coordinating activities	Activating and evaluating prior knowledge
Exploration	Repeating the previous topic	The teacher presents the general experience to the whole class
Explanation	New topic statement	Students will explain
Elaboration	Execution of the project	Applying ideas to new situations (independently)
Evaluation	The teacher evaluates the students' work	Both the teacher and students evaluate

The 5E model is an effective tool for developing a project-based approach to science, where students choose scientific projects based on their interests. Examples include exploring energy sources in physics, studying environmental projects in biology, or synthesizing new substances in chemistry. Each stage guides students toward solving scientific problems and allows them to connect theoretical knowledge with practice.

Literature Review on the Topic

There are many scientific studies and literature on approaches used in organizing project-based work on natural sciences. In particular, the effectiveness of the 5E approach, developed on the basis of the theory of constructivist pedagogy, has been confirmed by many scientific works. This approach was originally developed by Bybee, Laird, and Joseph (1997) and was presented as an innovative method of natural science education. Their studies showed that it is an effective tool for enhancing students' interests and directing them to scientific research [2], [3].

In addition, the 5E model has been introduced in Uzbekistan as a constructive approach that develops students' ability to apply knowledge in practice and independent thinking. In particular, local history scholar and educator O. Khamidov (2020) notes in his study that the 5E approach is important in strengthening students' theoretical knowledge on natural sciences. In their opinion, this model encourages students to actively engage in the subject and creates opportunities for independent learning through project work.[4]

Also, international studies conducted on the 5E approach confirm its effectiveness. For example, Harlen's (2010) study shows that the 5E model improves students' ability to expand and apply their knowledge. Each stage of the approach has been confirmed to be important in increasing students' interest and knowledge acquisition when teaching natural sciences.[3][5]

In conclusion, the literature analysis shows that the 5E approach is a powerful tool for the effective organization of project-based education in the natural sciences. In the scientific literature, this approach is described as an innovative model that develops students' abilities for independent research, application of knowledge in practice, and a deeper understanding of theoretical concepts.

-Research Methodology

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of the 5E approach in organizing project work in the field of natural sciences. The study was conducted based on methodological approaches and using empirical and theoretical methods. Empirical studies were aimed at monitoring students' scientific research and assessing their knowledge based on the project approach. Theoretical research was conducted by analyzing the main pedagogical aspects of the 5E approach and project-based education.

During the study, the process of classes and projects organized on the basis of the 5E model on natural sciences was observed through observations, and the activities and interests of students were analyzed. Interviews with teachers and students were organized using various questionnaires, their attitude and experience towards lesson processes based on the 5E model were studied.

As an experiment, a group of natural science students were offered a project based on the 5E approach, their work was assessed and the results were studied.

The study was conducted in the following stages:

Initial stage: The existing scientific literature on project-based learning and the 5E approach on natural sciences was analyzed and studied. The research methodology and sample groups were formed.

Practical stage: the process of lessons and projects organized on the basis of the 5E model was observed. Surveys of students and teachers were conducted. An experiment was conducted with the participation of students and the results of the project were analyzed.

Final stage: Based on the data obtained, the effectiveness of the 5E model was analyzed, the results were summarized and conclusions were made.

The data obtained from students and teachers were processed using statistical analysis tools, and the results of the study were expressed in the form of graphs and tables. The results of the experiment were assessed through qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Based on this methodology, the main goal of the study was successfully realized - to study the influence of the 5E approach on the process of student learning in the organization of project-based education in natural sciences and to evaluate its effectiveness.

Analysis and Results

During the research, observations and experiments were conducted to study how the level of students' learning and research abilities changed due to the application of the 5E approach to the project-based education process in natural sciences. The analysis and results based on the data obtained are presented below:

Results of the engagement stage:

The students started the new subject with interest, their interest in natural sciences increased significantly. Introduction to the topic with introductory questions and real-life examples based on the 5E approach helped to attract students' attention. Active question-answering and idea-sharing were observed.

Results of the exploration stage:

The students were given the opportunity to conduct experiments and practical work. At this stage, independent research in the field of natural sciences was carried out based on the 5E approach. The students' research abilities developed; they made many discoveries.

Results of the explanation stage:

The students began to explain new knowledge in their own words based on the information and experience they had collected. At this stage, students' ability to connect theoretical concepts with practice increased. The teacher explained the knowledge clearly and simply, and the students' knowledge was consolidated.

Results of the elaboration stage:

Students applied previously acquired knowledge to solve other problems. At this stage, students' creativity and independent thinking skills were developed through projects and practices. Students' projects allowed them to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

Results of the evaluation stage:

Students' knowledge and skills were assessed. At this stage, students assessed their knowledge through tests, questions and answers, and peer review.

The results show that the 5E approach to organizing project-based work on natural sciences effectively influences students' learning process and significantly improves their learning and research abilities [6].

Conclusion and recommendations

This research was devoted to studying the effectiveness of the 5E approach in organizing the project-based process of teaching natural sciences. The research results show that the 5E model is a very effective tool for developing students' research skills, applying theoretical knowledge in practice, and creating an interactive learning environment. [7] Students were active in the learning process and were able to independently expand their knowledge. The results obtained during the study confirm that the 5E approach can increase students' interest and create opportunities for their self-assessment.

Suggestions: It is necessary to regularly train teachers in organizing lessons using the 5E approach. This helps to improve their methodological skills [8].

During classes, it is necessary to try to increase students' interest through interactive methods, group work, and case studies.

Projects and competitions should be organized that stimulate students' research activities. Thanks to this, it is possible to develop students' creative and research skills [9].

It is necessary to develop new educational materials and resources compatible with the 5E approach, including expanding the use of online platforms.

In order to constantly monitor the effectiveness of lessons conducted based on the 5E approach and analyze the results, it is necessary to introduce systematic assessment mechanisms in schools [10].

REFERENCES

1. Vygotsky LS (1978). Reason in society: the development of higher psychological processes. Harvard University Press.
2. Bybee, R. W., Taylor, J. A., Gardner, A., Van Scotter, P., Powell, J. C., Westbrook, A., & Landes, N. (2006). The BSCS 5E Curriculum Model: Origins and Effectiveness. Colorado Springs: BSCS.

3. Harlen, W. (2010). *Teaching Science in the Elementary School*. Routledge.
4. Olkashunos, R., & Khamidov, S. (2020). *Using Constructive Pedagogical Approaches in Science Education*. Tashkent: Marifat Publishing House.
5. Bybee, R. W., & Landes, N. M. (1997). *Science for Life and Living: The Elementary School Science Program from the Biological Sciences Curriculum (BSCS)*. BSCS.
6. Trowbridge, L. W., Bybee, R. W., & Powell, J. C. (2008). *Teaching Science in the Middle Schools: Strategies for Developing Scientific Literacy*. Pearson/Merrill/Prentice Hall.
7. Gabel, D. (2003). *Handbook of Research on Science Teaching and Learning*. New York: Macmillan Publishing Company.
8. Kauchak, D., & Eggen, P. (2011). *Introduction to Teaching: Becoming a Professional*. Pearson Education.
9. Piaget, J. (1970). *Educational Science and the Psychology of the Child*. Orion Press.
10. Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and Education*. New York: Macmillan.